

JUDGING OF HOROSCOPE TOWARDS MEDICAL EDUCATION

C. Ananthi*, Prathiyangira Swamy Ji & K. Jothimani*****

School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies
(VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: C. Ananthi, Prathiyangira Swamy Ji & K. Jothimani, "Judging of Horoscope towards Medical Education", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 46-50, 2023.

Abstract:

A study of horoscope along with the nature of planets and their effect give correct guidance to the native in choosing right field of education or profession. It is the responsibility of the Sun to make a native self - confident and Mars makes him courageous. Jupiter is a divine planet that permits a native to administer medicine to another person curing him in a human manner. It is the Moon which permits a native to deal with poisonous substances and watch people who suffer with pain and diseases. As per the classical text, the 4th house is indicator of Education and 5th house indicates intelligence. The 10th house indicates karmasthana (karma to do in the life). 12th house indicates hospitals and beds. It is understood that the position of planets in the native's birth chart is the key factor to yield fruitful results to the natives at any case.

Key Words: Birth Chart, Aspects, Administer Medicine, Karmasthana

Astrology - Introduction:

Astrology deals with the planets Sun, Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, Saturn, Rahu and Ketu; Aswini and other constellations; Aries and other signs. Due to his constant searches and observations, man could recognize various planetary bodies, which are showing their effects on the living beings. Sun is a star. Earth and other planets are rotating around the Sun. The energies of the objects what we are using are seen with Godliness, then the reminiscence of that person will give pleasure and happiness. In this materialistic world we come across different kinds of people, different things but there may be certain resemblance among them. We understand with help of these resemblances and make certain classifications for analysing the nature of various planets. This classification helps us to understand the persons, article to gain knowledge, to learn something new, it gives good guidance in choosing the education and profession. In day-to-day life the signs of astrology is also made applicable in choosing proper education and profession.

Astrological Concepts for Medical Education:

The following houses and their lords support a person to do Medical Education. As per the classical text,

- The 4th house is indicator of Education and 5th house indicates intelligence.
- The 10th house indicates karma sthana (karma to do in the life)
- 12th house indicates hospitals and beds.
- The 5th house and the lord of 5th house.
- The lord of star in which lord of 5th house is placed.
- Influence of malefic planets Mars, Saturn and Rahu on the 5th house or on the 5th house lord.
- Influence of benefic planets on the 5th house lord.
- The 10th house and the lord on the 10th house.
- Planets in the 10th house and the placement of the lord of the 10th house.
- Influence of Malefic planets like Mars, Saturn and Rahu on the 10th house or the 10th house lord.
- Influence of benefic planets on the 10th house or on the 10th house lord.
- There should be a relation between 2nd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 9th and 10th houses or its lords.
- The connection of 5th and 10th house with 12th house.
- If 6th house or 6th lord makes relation with 10th house or its lord native becomes a doctor.
- Sun should be in good condition.
- Combination of Sun, moon, Jupiter and Mars in Kendra makes the person to do Medical / doctor Education.
- If Mars aspects or joins with 6th house or 6th house lord and 10th house or 10th house lord native will do Education in Medical surgeon.
- If Cancer, the sign of healing and nursing rules the native's 10th house or Lagna or 10th lord in Cancer gives Medical Education.
- Lagna or lagnesh, 6th house or 6th lord, 10th house or 10th lord and 12th house or 12th lord should connect with each other
- If 10th lord placed in Aswani Nakshatra as Aswani is the lord of medicine.
- If 5th and 6th house connected with each other it gives good intelligence for diagnosis of diseases.
- Any connection between Mars and Saturn at any house or placement or aspects or conjunction or Parivarthana, etc., in the horoscope.

- Any connection of Trikona Lords with 10th house.
- Influence of Jupiter on Kendra or Kona Lords or its houses.

Chart 1:

D.O.B: 18.09.1993 T.O.B:12.30 PM P.O.B: Arakkonam, T.N
 Time Zone: + 5.30 Lat: 13.N.04 Long: 79.E.39
 Education: M.B.B.S

		Ke				Ve		Me
						As		
						Ke		
Sa	Rashi Chart					Navamsa Chart		
					Su			Ju
As	Ra	Ma	Su			Ra	Mo	
		Mo	Me				Ma	
			Ju				Sa	

- Lagna Lord Jupiter conjunct with 10th house lord Mercury and placed in 10th house itself.
- Jupiter the lord of 1st house stationed in 10th house.
- Sun gets conjunct with 10th house lord mercury in 10th house itself.
- Conjunction of mars and moon in 11th house.
- Conjunction of sun and jupiter in 10th house.

Chart 2:

D.O.B: 22.10.1994 T.O.B: 12.02 AM P.O.B: Thiruvannamalai
 Time Zone: + 5.30 Lat: 13.N.04 Long: 80.E.16
 Education: M.B.B.S., M.D.

	Ke					Ve	Ju	
	Mo					Ra		
Sa	Rashi Chart			As		Navamsa Chart		
				Ma				
					Sa			
		Me Su			Mo	Su	Me	As
		Ra Ve				Ma	Ke	
		Ju						

- Mars showing its 8th aspects on Saturn.
- Jupiter placed in kendra, 4th house and aspects the 10th house.
- Jupiter the lord of 9th house aspects the 10th house.
- Jupiter the lord of 6th house aspects the 10th house.
- Sun aspects the 10th house.
- Sun and Jupiter conjunct together in 4th house and aspects the moon.

Chart 3:

D.O.B: 04.01.1997 T.O.B:11.10 AM P.O.B: Salem, T.N
 Time Zone: + 5.30 Lat: 11.N.39 Long.: 78.E.08
 Education: M.B.B.S., M.D.

As Sa						Ve		
Ke						Ra		
	Rashi Chart					Ma	Navamsa Chart	
						Mo		As
Ju						Ju		Me
Me	Ve	Mo	Ma				Su	Sa
Su			Ra					Ke

- Jupiter showing its 9th aspects on Mars.
- Saturn and moon having mutual aspects on each other.
- 9th lord mars showing its 4th aspects on 10th house.
- Jupiter aspects the 5th house, Trikona and 7th house Kendra.
- 6th lord sun placed in 10th house, Placement of sun in 10th house.

Chart 4:

D.O.B: 20.01.1993 T.O.B: 11.31PM P.O.B: Neyveli, T.N.
 Time Zone: + 5.30 Lat: 11.N.32 Long: 79.E.28
 Education: M.B.B.S., M.D.

		Ke	Ma		Su		Ve	
					Ma			
					Ra			
Ve	Rashi Chart				Me	Navamsa Chart		Ju
Me								
Su								
Sa								
Mo	Ra		As					Ke
			Ju					

- Mars showing its 8th aspects on 12th lord sun in 5th house.
- Jupiter aspects sun, mars aspects moon and jupiter.
- Mars showing its 8th aspects on saturn.
- 10th house lord mercury conjunct with 5th house lord saturn.
- Jupiter placed in 1st house and aspects the kendra and trikona houses 5,7,9.
- 6th lord saturn conjunct with 10th lord mercury in 5th house.

Chart 5:

D.O.B: 28.05.2000 T.O.B: 05.00 AM P.O.B: Sirkazhi, T.N.
 Time Zone: + 5.30 Lat: 11.N.14 Long: 79.E.44
 Education: M.B.B.S.

Mo	Ju	Ve	As		Ve	Su		
	Sa	Su	Me					
		Ma						
	Rashi Chart			Ra		Navamsa Chart		Mo
Ke					Ke			Ma
					Ju		Me	Ra
					Sa			

- 9th house lord Saturn conjunct with 10th house lord jupiter in Aries.
- Jupiter aspects Kendra and Trikona houses, 7th and 5th house respectively.
- Sun and mars conjunct and placed in 12th house and aspects the 6th house.

Chart 6:

D.O.B: 04.02.1986 T.O.B: 05.47 AM P.O.B: Virddhachalam
 Time Zone: + 5.30 Lat: 11.N.31 Long: 79.E.19
 Education: M.B.B.S., M.D.

	Ra				As			Ra
Ju	Rashi Chart					Navamsa Chart		Su
Su Me								
As Ve								
	Ma	Ke			Ke	Sa	Ju	Ma
	Sa					Mo		
	Mo							

- Conjunction of Mars and Saturn is seen in the horoscope.
- Conjunction of trikona lords, 5th and 9th lord, venus and mercury with the 10th lord venus.
- Jupiter aspects the kendra, the 10th house.
- 6th lord mercury conjunct with 10th lord venus.
- Mars conjunct with moon and shows its fourth aspect on jupiter.

Chart 7:

D.O.B: 21.11.1995 T.O.B: 07.20 AM P.O.B: Kozhikode, Kerala
 Time Zone: + 5.30 Lat: 12.N.59 Long: 77.E.35 Education: M.B.B.S.

	Ke				Ma	Ke	Sa			
					Ve					
Sa	Rashi Chart				Ju	Navamsa Chart		Me		
									Mo	Su
	As Me	Ra Mo			As		Ra			
	Su Ju									
	Ve Ma									

the above planets in appropriate houses and their aspects on them are responsible for medical education. Further, it is understood that though the position of planets are in good status, the Dasa period of the planets in the natives' birth chart is the key factor to yield fruitful results to the natives at any case.

Acknowledgement:

The authors wish to take this opportunity to express deepest sense of gratitude to School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India for providing necessary facilities to carry out this research work.

References:

1. BrahatParashara Hora Sasthra.
2. Phaladeepika
3. Three Hundred Important Combinations by Dr. B.V. Raman.
4. Jataka Chandrika.
5. Saravali.
6. Jathaga Parijatham by Vedhalinga Battar.